

SEPARATION OF COBALT FROM NICKEL USING ACETONE AS A SOLVENT

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Separation of cobalt from nickel has been effected by using acetone as a solvent. The method is based upon the principle that cobalt chloride is highly soluble in acetone while nickel chloride is insoluble in the same solvent.

In continuation of our work on the separation of calcium from strontium using acetone as a solvent (Tillu and Telang, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 19, 231), it has been found out that acetone can also be used to separate cobalt from nickel.

In the estimation of cobalt the main difficulty is to obtain cobalt in the form of its compound entirely free from nickel (Friend, "Text Book of Inorganic Chemistry", Vol. IX, Part I, p. 75). Although many methods of their separation are found in literature, they are either complicated, or involve the use of very costly and complex organic compounds, which cannot be easily accessible in the purest condition. Moreover, they are not without their limitations. This new method of separation is simple, cheaper, and is applicable irrespective of the amount of nickel present.

Nickel chloride is insoluble in acetone while cobalt chloride is highly soluble. It follows therefore that the two elements should be present in the mixture as dry chlorides. If they are not initially present as chlorides they have to be converted into dry chlorides. Thus after separation by this method cobalt or nickel can be estimated by the usual method.

EXPERIMENTAL

The order of solubility of nickel chloride in acetone as found by the author at 35° is 1 part in 16000 parts of acetone. Cobalt chloride is highly soluble.

Various mixtures of cobalt chloride and nickel chloride were prepared in aqueous solution and the results of analysis have been recorded in the accompanying table.

A known quantity of cobalt chloride solution (about 2%) was taken in a weighing bottle and evaporated to dryness at 110°, the weight of the residue corresponding to the amount of cobalt chloride taken (Friend, *ibid.*, p. 39). To this residue of cobalt chloride ($\text{CoCl}_2, \text{H}_2\text{O}$) again a known quantity of nickel chloride solution in dilute hydrochloric acid (about 2%) was added and evaporated to dryness at 110° (Ditte, *Ann. Chim. Phys.*, 1881, v, 22, 551). The weight of this residue less the weight of cobalt chloride taken gives the weight of nickel chloride ($\text{NiCl}_2, \text{H}_2\text{O}$).

The mixture of dry chlorides was prepared by evaporation at 110°. Cobalt chloride was extracted with acetone from nickel chloride and the filtration was done through a sintered glass crucible. The acetone solution was evaporated to dryness in a previously weighed platinum

dish and the residual cobalt chloride was further dried at 110° , and weighed as such. The nickel chloride left behind after extraction in the sintered glass crucible was dried and weighed.

TABLE I

Mixture No.	CoCl ₂ , H ₂ O		NiCl ₂ , H ₂ O	
	Actual.	Found.	Actual.	Found.
I	0.1300	0.1290	0.1700	0.1713
II	0.0663	0.0658	0.1720	0.1715
III	0.1324	0.1320	0.0844	0.0840
IV	0.0668	0.0653	0.2545	0.2535
V	0.1064	0.1070	0.0831	0.0838
VI	0.0656	0.0646	0.3450	0.3446
VII	0.2652	0.2648	0.0838	0.0832
VIII	0.1332	0.1328	0.2550	0.2542
IX	0.2660	0.2654	0.1320	0.1333

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